

Improving energy efficiency of MPDATA on GPU-based supercomputers using mixed precision arithmetic

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In this work, we propose a method that allows us to decrease the energy consumption in supercomputing centers. Our method is based on applying the mixed precision arithmetic, and its use is demonstrated for a real-life scientific application called MPDATA. All the tests are executed on two GPU-based clusters. The first one, the Piz Daint supercomputer ranked 8th at the TOP500 list (Nov. 2016), is equipped with the most powerful GPU accelerators - NVIDIA Tesla P100 that are based on the NVIDIA Pascal GPU architecture. The second one, the MICLAB cluster, is equipped with the most advanced Kepler based GPUs - NVIDIA Tesla K80.

Our research shows that using the proposed technique we are able to provide a very high accuracy of computation and significantly decrease the energy consumption. The correctness and accuracy of our implementation are examined in a standard 3D solid body rotation test case.

1 Introduction

The energy consumption is a critical issue due to the significant increase of operation costs in modern computer systems [2]. In consequence, reducing the energy consumption turns into the primary objective for scientific and industrial environments, which are related to large-scale calculations. It is estimated that reducing the energy consumption by one megawatt could save about 1 million \$ per year. Given the rapidly climbing power bills, as well as the negative impact of energy production technologies on the environment, achieving power and energy efficiency of parallel systems and applications has become one of the most challenging issues.

In this work, we focus on reducing the energy consumption in big supercomputing centers. We would like to propose to consider this issue from the point of view of average users. Therefore, we need to face with a common problem for users of such centers. A lot of approaches to reducing the energy consumption require some special user authorizations to apply techniques required to modify the hardware configuration (frequency, switching nodes off, powering cores down). However, an average user does not have access to change such characteristics while executing his/her time and energy consuming simulations.

2 Problem Overview

We propose to apply the mixed precision arithmetic [10, 4] under some constraints to reduce the energy consumption. The constraints are related to the accuracy of simulations expressed by three types of errors: diffusion error, phase error, and L2 norm. The

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correctness of our technique is examined based on a real-life scientific applications, Multidimensional Positive Definite Advection Transport Algorithm (MPDATA) [9], with a standard 3D solid body rotation test case.

The 3D MPDATA application corresponds to an iterative algorithm that solves the continuity equation describing the advection of a nondiffusive quantity Ψ in a flow field:

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial t} + \text{div}(V\Psi) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where V is the velocity vector that is stored in three separate arrays $v1$, $v2$, and $v3$; each of them stores the velocity in one direction: i , j , and k , respectively.

MPDATA is the main module of the multiscale fluid model EULAG [5]. The model is an innovative solver in the field of numerical modeling of multiscale atmospheric flows. The algorithm is positive defined and by appropriate flux correction can be also monotonic. This is a desirable feature for advection of positive definite variables such as specific humidity, cloud water, cloud ice, rain, snow, aerosol particles, and gaseous substances. The spatial discretization of MPDATA is based on finite difference approximations. The algorithm is iterative and fast convergent.

In fact, to implement this algorithm we use 11 arrays: $v1, v2, v3, f1, f2, f3$ represents velocities in each direction ($f1, f2, f3$ are required to store intermediate results); x, xP correspond to the scalar quantity Ψ (xP - output of the odd iteration or time step of MPDATA, and input of the even time step; x - vice versa); h represents the vector of density, while cp, cn store intermediate results. Our current GPU implementation [6] consists of 4 GPU kernels which perform a sequence of stencil computations.

The proposed implementation of MPDATA is examined using the standard 3D solid-body rotation test [8], in which a sphere of radius R is advected with a constant angular velocity $\omega = 0.1$ around the domain diagonal axis. The velocity field is stationary and divergent free. The initial distribution of the tracer inside the sphere is defined as $\Psi(r) = 4(1 - r/R)$, where r is the distance from the center of the sphere.

Our numerical simulations have been performed at regular grids ($\Delta x = \Delta y = \Delta z$) with different resolution, namely $41^3, 81^3, 121^3$. The size of time step depends on the grid resolution. Assuming the grid spacing equal to 2 ($\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z = 2$) and the time increment $\Delta t = 0.2$, we estimate the maximum value of the Courant number as $C_r = 0.29$.

To quantify the accuracy of numerical results we use the following statistical measures:

- phase error defined as the distance between the exact maximum position (at $t = 0$) and that computed after one full rotation:

$$R_{phase} = \sqrt{(i^{start} - i^{end})^2 + (j^{start} - j^{end})^2 + (k^{start} - k^{end})^2} \quad (2)$$

- diffusion error (q represents the quantity Ψ):

$$R_{diff} = \max(q^{start}) - \max(q^{end}) \quad (3)$$

- L2-norm:

$$R_{L2} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_i (q_i^{start} - q_i^{end})^2} \quad (4)$$

3 Main Contribution

This approach is aiming at reducing the energy consumption beyond using hardware-dependent methods. The advantage of our method is that it does not require any special user authorizations. Thanks to that it can be widely applied to most advanced supercomputing centers by all the users with the standard access. The proposed method minimizes the energy consumption by selecting the precision for each of the MPDATA arrays. Decreasing the precision from double to float decreases the size of an array by the factor of two, as well as memory traffic, while the execution time is reducing by a factor depending on hardware platforms, since the single precision arithmetic is twice faster than the double one using NVIDIA Tesla P100 GPUs and three times faster for Kepler-based GPUs.

Our assumptions are as follows:

- reducing the precision for an array reduces the simulation accuracy;
- reducing the precision for an array decrease the energy consumption;
- reducing the precision for a number of arrays at once has different impact on the simulation accuracy and energy consumption compared to separate reductions.

The constraints are presented below:

- the phase error R_{phase} should not exceed the distance between two nodes in the computational grid;
- the diffusion error R_{diff} should be lower than $R_{diff}^{double} + \Delta R_{diff}$;
- the value R_{L2} of L2-norm should be lower than $R_{L2}^{double} + \Delta R_{L2}$.

As a rule of thumb, we propose to increase the values of errors R_{diff} , R_{L2} by ΔR_{diff} , $\Delta R_{L2} = 0.15$ in relation to the errors R_{diff}^{double} , R_{L2}^{double} achieved using the double precision format.

To implement the proposed method, the following procedure is executed for MPDATA:

1. Execute the test run using the double precision arithmetic for all the arrays.
2. Execute 11 tests: for each test set one array to float.
3. Run an estimator to select a near optimal solution.
4. If errors are too high, then increase the precision for the last array changed by the estimator; otherwise, decrease the precision for the first array unchanged by the estimator.
5. Repeat steps 3-4 until two consecutive iterations return the same set of precisions.

The estimator collects data from the tests, including the values of energy consumption and errors, and calculates the ratio $r = \delta E / \delta R_{L2}$ for each array, where δE and δR_{L2} are differences between respectively the energy consumption and L2-norm measured for the double and float formats. Then the estimator sorts the arrays by the ratio r , from the highest to the lowest. Finally, it sets the arrays (in the sorted order) to float until the adopted constraints are satisfied, and executes a new test using the new precisions for the selected arrays.

The preliminary tests were performed using the CUDA+MPI environment on the Piz Daint supercomputer [1] equipped with NVIDIA P100 GPUs, and MICLAB cluster

[3] containing NVIDIA K80 GPUs. These tests show that our method allows reducing the energy consumed by the application from 25% to 35% on Piz Daint and from 33% to 43% on MICLAB, considering only the energy consumed by the graphic cards. Furthermore, it allows users to decrease the energy consumption resulted from their simulations without any special access to machines such as the superuser account. Using the mixed precision arithmetic, our approach based permits us to achieve the energy reduction at the similar level as the DVFS technique investigated in paper [7]. What is also important, unlike the DVFS technique, the proposed method reduces the execution time of MPDATA.

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